

Identification of M&E indicators, and creation of M&E tool (MS.15)

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List of abbreviations

CFD	Climate Farm Demo
NC	National Coordinator
PDF	Pilot Demo Farmer
WP	Work Package
CFA	Climate Farm Advisor
ME&L	Monitoring, Evaluation & Learning
CSF	Climate Smart Farming
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System
OFD	On Farm Demonstration
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
NAM	National Annual Meeting

Abstract

The Climate Farm Demo (CFD) project supports the delivery of 4,500 high quality demonstration events across 1,500 pilot demonstration farms (PDFs). Work Package (WP) 3, task 3.3, focuses on learning from and continuously improving climate farm demo activities by **Monitoring, Evaluating and Learning** (ME&L). This milestone provides tools for ME&L at different stages of the project:

- Reference to existing **Farm demo Tools and Training Kits** to support Climate Smart Farm demos and improve skills
- ME&L tool to be used during the **National Annual Meeting** for Evaluating CSF demo practices on a national level
- **In-depth case interviews** with CSAs and PDFs to gather in-depth data on Climate Farm Demonstration effectiveness
- An **Exit Poll** to measure the impact of climate smart demo events on the adoption of climate smart practices by European farmers

We expect the following outputs as a result of these ME&L activities:

- Necessary **Trainings** for CFAs and NCs
- **CSF demonstration improvements** throughout the course of the project
- Practical **Leaflets** that address the question of how to specifically demonstrate CSF practices
- **Recommendations for Climate Farm Demo activities**

Chapter 1

Introduction

The Climate Farm Demo (CFD) project supports the delivery of 4,500 high quality demonstration events across 1,500 pilot demonstration farms (PDFs). Work Package (WP) 3, task 3.3, focuses on learning from and continuously improving climate farm demo activities by **Monitoring, Evaluating and Learning** (ME&L) from previous demonstrations to increase their quality over the project's timespan. With the demonstrations we want to substantially increase the uptake and application of Climate Smart Farming (CSF) approaches and practices by other PDFs and 'average' farmers through peer-to-peer learning at partner, national and EU-level, thereby increasing the impact of CSF demos within and beyond the project.

High quality and impactful demo activities are necessary to efficiently share knowledge regarding CSF practices and to facilitate learning amongst farmers. The quality and impact of demo events is highly dependent on specific factors such as the degree of interaction and facilitation, structural set-up and group dynamics of an event [1]. Therefore, the overall **goal** of ME&L in CFD is to improve the quality and impact of climate smart farming demo activities. Based on lessons learned from the ME&L during the demo years, the dynamic ME&L tools can be adjusted or replaced over the project's timespan. In terms of **outcomes and outputs**, the priority of ME&L in CFD is to continuously improve the quality of the farm demonstration events and learn how to effectively demonstrate climate smart farming practices. Secondly, we intend to share these insights within and beyond the project, for example by producing leaflets that outline good examples of demonstrating CSF practices.

Definitions

Demo activity quality

The quality of demonstration events can be defined by multiple factors ensuring demo efficacy. This concerns the quality of demo facilitation, the recognition of different learning styles of the participants and practical considerations for a smooth operation of the event [2]. Using ME&L, the quality of demo events will be empirically improved over the course of the CFD project.

Demo activity impact

The term 'impact' refers to "significant or lasting changes in people's lives, brought about by a given action or series of actions" [3]. In the context of demonstration events, impact refers to significant or lasting changes in adoption of Climate Smart Farming practices by farmer and AKIS actors using real life conditions [1]. Previous research has shown that OFD are an effective way to stimulate innovation adoption [10], thereby increasing uptake of CSF practices. Using ME&L, both the quality and subsequent impact of demonstrations will be improved over the course of the CFD project.

On Farm Demonstration

On Farm Demonstrations (OFDs) are events where innovations or novel practices or ways of thinking are displayed. OFDs facilitate farmer-to-farmer learning. Within CFD, the goal of OFDs is to accelerate the adoption of climate smart farming practices and solutions.

Core concepts

To change towards CSF practices to help farmers respond effectively to climate change, WP1 describes the ADKAR model using five different steps of change (Figure 1). The stage in this model can be used to refer to the stage in which PDF demonstrate CSF practices.

Figure 1. ADKAR model for indicating Climate Smart Farming practices on demonstration farms.

Over the course of the project, the goal for WP3, task 3.3., is to move further 'to the right' in the ADKAR model: from awareness and precontemplation towards reinforcement and maintenance. OFD events are particularly useful for knowledge exchange, support ability to implement CSF on farm level and facilitate reinforcement from other CS-AKIS actors. Of course, there are many other related activities such as education, formal advisory support, that further support all elements of the ADKAR model. After analysing the ME&L results, we can develop necessary training, tools, etc. to facilitate CFAs in more effectively facilitating demo events and create higher impact, moving towards reinforcement from other CS-AKIS actors and maintaining lessons learned.

For ME&L we focus on three core concepts related to demonstrating climate action in farm demonstration events: transformative learning, systemic change, and impact & climate action. These three concepts are relevant in creating complex change in the context of climate smart farming practices. The three core concepts are used in developing the ME&L tools and will also be used in the analysis and subsequent WP3 project interventions; e.g.: is there a need to further facilitate transformative learning? Can we provide good examples of how to demonstrate complex change in the context of CSF? Or, how can we further improve the quality and impact of CSF demos?

Transformative learning

Transformative learning is a theory of learning, focusing on adult education and young adult learning. The theory is based on the idea that learners can adjust their thinking and perspective based on new information. The founder of transformative learning [4] defined it as *"an orientation which holds that the way learners interpret and reinterpret their sense experience is central to making meaning and hence learning."*

The above-mentioned theory and empirical studies show that **deliberately facilitating dialogue** during OFDs (On Farm Demos) between farmers and other participants, increases stimulation of transformative learning processes, compared to OFDs during which dialogue is not deliberately facilitated [5]. When engaging in transformative learning, learners question their **deeply held assumptions** and are subsequently **changed by the experience** [6]. This change, or perspective

transformation, can occur either through an accumulation of transformed cognitive meaning schemes or because of an acute personal or social crisis (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Transformative learning process.

According to the theory on transformative learning, it is only through **critical reflection** “that we can fully exploit the immanent potential of the knowledge and information at our disposal in an empowering and even emancipatory way” [5]. Within CFD, demo farms are used as learning spaces. By interviewing CFAs and PDFs, we hope to gain insights into how effective demo farms are in performing this function.

With improving the demonstration events in CFD using the ME&L, we want to contribute to transformative learning about CSF practices to eventually increase the uptake of CSF approaches in the EU. Moreover, the transformative learning core concept will be implemented in ME&L to improve the demonstration learning process to transform farming practices into CSF practices.

Systemic change

Systemic change is “an intentional process designed to alter the status quo by shifting and realigning the form and function of a targeted system.” [6] In most system changes, the underlying **structures** and **supporting mechanisms** that operate within a system are **altered**, such as the policies, routines, relationships, resources, power structures, and values [7].

For systemic change it is important to create a rich picture of stakeholder perspectives. Specific for the context of farm demonstrations it is important to gain insight into stakeholder interpretations of the climate issue and possible on farm solutions. For OFD, this means that these perspectives and contextualisations need to be taken into account during a demo. The process of systemic change is as much of a process rather than an end state. Therefore, an iterative ME&L approach is necessary. Systemic change in the context of EU farming practices can be defined changing the farming system, on both individual farm level as well as national and EU-level (including the AKIS), towards a CSF practice system. This is different from an approach where sub-problems are addressed separately. For example, a farmer looking to reduce inputs may explore technical solutions, but also new ways of working together with peers, new ways of financing innovation, exploring waste streams as resources, etc. The ME&L focuses on systemic change to work towards and reflect on the extent to which demonstration activities contribute to systemic change regarding CSF practices. With improving demonstration events based on the systemic change framework, farmers and stakeholders are likely to alter their underlying structures and mechanism towards CSF in the near future.

Impact and climate action

Multiple definitions exist for the core concept ‘impact’. Established literature in international development and evaluation often uses the term to refer to “*significant or lasting changes in people’s*

lives, brought about by a given action or series of actions.” [3] More recently, impact has also come to be associated with results that target the “root causes” of a social problem [8].

CFD as a project has formulated the ambitious climate goal to strengthen European farmers' capacities to implement, demonstrate and uptake of CSF practice across the EU and reduce significantly their greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (by up to 35%) along the project life, thus achieving the EU 2030 Climate Target Plan. To achieve this goal, climate action (in the form of CSF) is needed. Through monitoring and evaluating demo events in CFD, we learn about effective ways to demonstrate CSF and increase positive climate impact.

In this ME&L method, we assume that CSF demo activity impact will be increased by improving the on farm demonstrations and its effectiveness. Peer-to-peer learning activities and facilitation during the demo event increases the participant's perception of the effectiveness of a demonstration event [1,2]. Research shows that the key factors for improving on farm demo effectiveness are: 1) interaction and facilitation (facilitator autonomy, relatedness, and competence), 2) demo structure (day structure, available time for activities and time management, group size) and 3) group dynamics.

With developing these aspects in demonstrating CSF practices using the ME&L tools, the impact of CSF demo activities is likely to improve. When we talk about impact in the context of Monitoring, Evaluation & Learning about Climate Smart Demo events, we are therefore not intending to take quantitative measure on farms to measure the contribution of demos within CFD to decreased GHG emissions. Rather, we will measure impact by collecting data on 1) intention of demo participants to adopt CSF practices; and 2) facilitating transformative learning that will increase demo effectiveness. Facilitating transformative learning will be done by firstly identifying learning needs and consequently providing training or other types of support to further improve transformative learning qualities (e.g. how to facilitate a dialogue).

Chapter 2

Planning

To meet the goal of Task 3.3, a set of activities are planned throughout each project year to monitor and evaluate the on farm demonstrations on a national and international level. The ME&L approach collects quantitative, qualitative, and descriptive information from the multiple actors involved in each demo activity as described by the different activities shown in Table 11.

Table 1. Monitoring, Evaluating & Learning activities given the timing, activity, tool, actors involved and main goal.

Activity	When	Tool	Responsible	Goal
Annual ME&L session with all Advisors	In every National Annual Meeting (NAM) from the 2nd CFD year - Start in 2024	National Annual ME&L tool	CFA, NC	Evaluate how to improve the demonstration of CSF practices through national group reflection
Using Farm Demo Training Kit	Throughout the demo years	D3.1, all tools on https://trainingkit.farmdemo.eu/	CFA	Improve planning and delivery of demonstration events
ME&L at demonstration events	After 10% of demos, each demo year	Exit poll	CFA	Quantitatively tracking progress during project + indication on WP3 training focus
In depth case-interviews with CFAs & PDF	Throughout the course of the project	Interview guide	WP3, Task 3.3	In-depth understanding of effective climate-smart farming demos; collect good practices, understand how to demonstrate system change, facilitate transformative learning, and create impact.

The timeline above provides an indicative overview of ME&L activities during the course of the CFD project. Note that the ME&L approach is dynamic, so tools and interventions may be added or changed throughout the course of the project.

Chapter 3

Farm demo Tools and Training Kits

Support your Climate Smart Farm demos and improve your skills

Demo Design Guide for Climate Farm Project On-Farm Demonstrations

Deliverable 3.1 of CFD provides a **Demo Design Guide** specifically for on-farm CSF demonstrations. In this deliverable you can find step-by-step tips and explanations about:

1. Planning the demo event
2. Making the best use of the host farmer
3. Farm demo setup
4. Promotion of events
5. Learning and facilitation methods
6. Monitoring, Evaluation and Follow-up

This design guide provides you with a blueprint to support the delivery of demonstration events. You can find tips and examples of how to successfully plan, deliver and evaluate a CSF demo event.

In previous Farm Demo projects, many lessons have been learned about organising and facilitating on-farm demo events. Within these projects, many ready-to-use tools have been developed to support farm demo organisers in organising effective demo events. These tools are available in all EU national languages and can be found at: <https://trainingkit.farmdemo.eu/>.

To guide you towards helpful tools, we provide you with a short overview of tools to use in preparation of a demo event, during a demo event and tools for evaluation and follow-up.

Tools for preparing a demo event

Planning and preparing a demo event involves four important steps¹:

1. Specifying the objective of the demo event
2. Finding a good host
3. Defining the organising team
4. Promotion of your event

In the Farm Demo Training kit you can find tools, ranging from guidelines for communicating about the event to a template for registration forms with informed consent.

Tools for delivering a demo event

When delivering a demo event, keep in mind the following three basic rules²:

1. Relate the learning content to a climate smart farming practice
2. Engage participants in active knowledge exchange
3. Use a variety of learning methods

Tools and guidelines for a variety of learning methods can be found in the FarmDemo Training kit.

¹ <https://trainingkit.farmdemo.eu/tools-for-preparing-a-demo-event/>

² <https://trainingkit.farmdemo.eu/tools-for-delivering-a-demo-event>

Tools for evaluation and follow-up

Evaluation and follow-up of a demo event is important to increase the impact of your demo event. You can achieve higher impact of your demo events in two ways³:

1. Improve demo events by performing self-assessment (post-event);
2. Making sure that key messages stick with the participants by organising follow-up activities.

Monitoring tools, observation checklists, tools for team reflection can be found in the Farm Demo Training kit⁴.

³ <https://trainingkit.farmdemo.eu/tools-for-evaluation-and-follow-up/>

⁴ <https://trainingkit.farmdemo.eu/>

Chapter 4

National Annual Meeting

Evaluating CSF demo practices on a national level using the ME&L tool

The national annual meeting will be used to explore how to effectively demonstrate Climate Smart Farming practices on a national level with all national CFAs. Using a handout, we focus on two entry points for the ME&L: 1) the individual demo farm and behaviour, and 2) the enabling environment surrounding the demo farm.

Goal: To evaluate how to effectively demonstrate CSF practices.

Annual meeting script

In preparation of the National Annual Meeting

In preparation of the National Annual Meeting, the National Coordinator needs to prepare the Monitoring and Evaluation session.

It is necessary that PDF and CFA participate in the session. Based on the attendance of other participants (AKIS) in the National Annual Meeting, you can choose to involve them in ME&L or organise a breakout session with the PDF and CFA to evaluate last demonstration year.

You can use the following checklist when preparing the meeting:

- Look up your country's main climate issue as defined during the first National Annual Meeting, as formulated during the first NAM and facilitated by WP1.
- Print out the ME&L hexagon tool on A0 format or on multiple A4 formats if you are not able to print A0.
- NB: Group size and geographical distribution of project participants differ between countries. This will influence the way in which the NAM will be organised (physically or online) and consequently the way in which ME&L can be effectively performed during the NAM. If the NAM will be attended by a large group, you can choose to duplicate the tool and fill-it in in subgroups.

The ME&L hexagon tool can be found in PDF format on the SharePoint in the WP3 folder.

- Collect post-its, pens, and other tools you think might be useful to carry out the ME&L session.
 - Prepare the ME&L session using the script in the next section.
- It is necessary that PDF and CFA will participate in the session. Based on the attendance of other participants in the National Annual Meeting, you can choose to involve them in ME&L or organise a breakout session with the PDF and CFA to evaluate last demonstration year.

During the National Annual Meeting

National Annual Meeting				
Monitoring, Evaluation & Learning script				
Timing	What	How	Who	Materials
5 min	Introduction	<p>Introduce the ME&L tool and goal: <i>The overall goal of Monitoring, Evaluation & Learning in CFD is to improve the quality and impact of climate smart farming demo activities.</i></p> <p>During the National Annual Meetings, we collect lessons learned specifically about demonstration Climate Smart Farming practices from each country participating in CFD.</p>	National coordinator	If you want, you can prepare a short PowerPoint, but it is not necessary for the process. If you do, keep it short and simple so most time can be spent on the collective evaluation of the past demo year
5 min	Explanation of ME&L tool	Shortly explain the group reflection process	National coordinator	National Annual Meeting M ME&L hexagon Tool, printed on A0 format
60 min	Group reflection on the past demo year	<p>Discuss the questions below, following the hexagon tool in a clockwise direction. For each question, you can ask each participant to first write their input on a post-it, put it on the hexagon tool and then discuss. <i>NB. If a large group is attending the meeting, split up the group in subgroups of around 10-15 people and ask them to fill in the hexagon tool in the subgroups.</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 0. Fill in your country's main climate issue (as defined during the first National Annual Meeting). Have you defined multiple climate issues? Then you can choose 1 (e.g., based on preference or chose the most pressing issue) 1. Ask all CFAs and PDFs⁵ to provide 1 demo example(s): How did you demonstrate climate smart farming practices to tackle your national climate issue? Describe the example in detail, so this example can be used in other cases with the same climate issue. 	Facilitated by the national coordinator, input from CFAs and attending demo farmers	National Annual Meeting ME&L hexagon Tool, printed on A0 format or hand out multiple (A4) formats to sub groups Post-its, pens

⁵ In some countries, a wider audience including other AKIS actors may be invited to the NAM. PDFs and CFAs should always be involved in the ME&L session. It is up to you if you want to also involve the other AKIS actors or not.

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Ask all CFAs and PDFs to share 1 highlight of the past demo year. Here we ask for specific elements of CSF practices that worked well for your country's climate issue. e.g., open discussion, professional facilitator, open workspace, field trip, etc. 3. Ask all CFAs and PDFs to share 1 main challenge in demonstrating solutions for the central climate issue during the past demo year. Here we ask for specific elements of CSF practices that were a challenge for demonstrating the climate issue. E.g., too many/less visitors, no clear goal, no real-life examples, etc. 4. Ask all CFAs and PDFs to share what they want to improve in the coming year to build on successes and address challenges. This information will be used as a basis for new trainings and ME&L tools over the course of the CFD project. 5. Ask all CFAs and demo farmers what support they need to improve the Climate Smart Farming demos (skills, tools, etc.). 6. Ask all CFAs and PDFs if there is anything else they want to get off their chest. 		
5 min	Closing	Very shortly summarise the discussion and close the ME&L exercise		

After the National Annual Meeting

After organising a national annual meeting, it is important to collect all data for ME&L. Therefore, we ask each country to fill in this simplified table (in English) of the ME&L tool and mail it to ellen.bulten@wur.nl and emma.knol@wur.nl after each annual meeting.

Questions from tool	Collected answers from annual meeting
<p>Ask all CFAs and PDFs to provide 1 demo example(s): How did you demonstrate climate smart farming practices to tackle your national climate issue? Describe the example in detail, so this example can be used in other cases with the same climate issue.</p>	
<p>Ask all CFAs and PDFs to share 1 highlight of the past demo year. Here we ask for specific elements of CSF practices that worked well for your country's climate issue. e.g., open discussion, professional facilitator, open workspace, field trip, etc.</p>	
<p>Ask all CFAs and PDFs to share 1 main challenge in demonstrating solutions for the central climate issue during the past demo year. Here we ask for specific elements of CSF practices that were a challenge for demonstrating the climate issue. E.g., too many/less visitors, no clear goal, no real-life examples, etc.</p>	
<p>Ask all CFAs and PDFs to share what they want to improvement in the coming year. This information will be used as a basis for new trainings and ME&L tools over the course of the CFD project.</p>	
<p>Ask all CFAs and demo farmers what support they need to improve the Climate Smart Farming demos. Skills, tools, etc.</p>	
<p>Ask all CFAs and PDFs if there is anything else they want to get off their chest.</p>	

Handout – National Annual meeting

Chapter 5

In-depth case interviews

In-depth data on Climate Farm Demonstration effectiveness

For getting a better understanding of the effectiveness of CSF demos, in-depth interviews will be held with a selection of CFAs and host farmers throughout the demo years. Moreover, we want to collect good practices, understand how to demonstrate systemic change, facilitate transformative learning and create impact.

Goal: In-depth understanding of effective climate-smart farming demos.

Interview guide and questions

Introduction interview	
For monitoring and evaluating the Climate Farm demonstrations in Climate Farm Demo, we want to get an in-depth understanding of effective climate-smart farming demos. Since you are the Climate Farm Advisor in your country, we want to ask you some additional question.	
Introductory questions	Answers
1. Can you introduce yourself and tell me something about how your daily work relates to Climate Smart Farming practices?	
2. How many CFD demonstration events did you facilitate/organise in the past year?	
In-depth questions	Answers
3. What main climate issue was tackled in your demonstrations?	
4. What climate smart farming practices were demonstrated in your demonstrations?	
5. Can you give a good example of how a climate smart farming practice was demonstrated? What did you see/hear/touch/experience? How did you involve the host farmer, or use their farm, their data in the demo event? What steps did you take to engage the participants in the demo event? How did you make this work? Why was it a good example?	
6. Expectations: What was the main aim of this successful demo? E.g.: inform, awareness raising, convince, facilitate action, etc.	
7. Looking back, what worked well in demonstrating Climate Smart Farming practices, what didn't, and why? How do you know that it worked well (or didn't)? How did you evaluate the demo event? What follow-up activities did you perform with the event participants following the demo event?	
8. Do you have a suggestion of a host farmer to be interviewed? - Speaks English - Organised a CSF demo within CFD	

Chapter 6

Exit Poll

Measuring the impact of climate smart demo events on the adoption of climate smart practices by European farmers

Goal: Measuring the impact of the CSD events on the adoption of CSF practises in the EU.

To measure the impact of climate smart demo events on the adoption of CSF practices by European farmers, ME&L exit polls will be used at the end of demonstration events. Demonstration exit polls give us a quick quantitative insight in the demonstration progress and its impact on visitors leading to CSF practices. Furthermore, it gives an indication on where to focus WP3 trainings on.

Exit polls will be used in approximately **10%** of the demonstration events for each country (Table 2). NCs are responsible for making CSAs aware of these exit polls and to ensure the appropriate number of polls are completed every demo year. After a demonstration event, the exit poll will be shared with the demonstration visitors via a QR code (to be filled in online directly after a demo event, using a mobile phone) or email. Filling in the poll will take around 3-4 minutes.

Table 2. Number of exit polls for each country per demonstration year.

	Country	Total demo events in CFD	Number of exit polls at the end of CFD	Number of exit polls per demo year*
1	Austria	75	8	1-2
2	Belgium	180	18	3
3	Bulgaria	75	8	1-2
4	Croatia	75	8	1-2
5	Denmark	180	18	3
6	Estonia	75	8	1-2
7	Finland	75	8	1-2
8	France	390	39	6-7
9	Germany	390	39	6-7
10	Greece	180	18	3
11	Hungary	75	8	1-2
12	Ireland	180	18	3
13	Italy	390	39	6-7
14	Latvia	75	8	1-2
15	Lithuania	75	8	1-2
16	Luxemburg	75	8	1-2
17	Netherlands	180	18	3
18	Poland	390	39	6-7
19	Portugal	75	8	1-2
20	Romania	180	18	3
21	Slovakia	75	8	1-2
22	Slovenia	75	8	1-2
23	Spain	390	39	6-7
24	Sweden	75	8	1-2
25	Switzerland	75	8	1-2
26	United Kingdom	390	39	6-7

*exit polls need to be done every demo year, so with 6 demo years, countries with 75 total demo events need to do an exit poll at 1 or 2 events each year, countries with 180 total demo events need to do 3 exit polls each year and countries with 390 total demo events need to do 6 or 7 exit polls each year.

Below you find the content of the exit poll. Note that this is just an indicative overview, the final exit poll will be provided digitally.

Introductory

1. Language	Drop-down menu with all national languages
2. Country	Drop-down menu with all 27 participating countries
3. Thematic area of the demo:	Drop-down menu: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grassland management - Forage production - Crops management - Soil health and biodiversity - Agroforestry and relation to landscape - Energy management - Biogas production - Water management - Herd management - Manure storage and spreading - Additives for reducing enteric methane emissions - Rewarding mechanisms

Level of understanding

Please rate your level of understanding of the demo topic **BEFORE** and **AFTER** today's event:

- 1 = Very little understanding about topic
- 2 = Basic understanding – need to know more
- 3 = Reasonable understanding - but would not be confident about putting into use
- 4 = Good understanding - would put into use but not be very confident
- 5 = Very good understanding – would be very confident about putting into use

4. What was your level of understanding about the demo topic before and after the event?	BEFORE event					AFTER event				
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5

Current climate actions

5. Have you already implemented climate actions within the following thematic areas on your own farm?

Thematic areas	Yes	No	N.A.
1 Grassland management			
2 Forage production			
3 Crops management			
4 Soil health and biodiversity			
5 Agroforestry and relation to landscape			
6 Energy management			
7 Biogas production			
8 Water management			
9 Herd management			
10 Manure storage and spreading			
11 Additives for reducing enteric methane emissions			
12 Rewarding mechanisms			

Future climate actions

	Very unlikely	Unlikely	Neutral	Likely	Very Likely
6. How likely are you to implement the climate smart practices as demonstrated during the demo on your farm in the coming 6 to 12 months?					
7. How likely are you to recommend the demonstrated practices to other farmers?					

Future needs

8. Please indicate to what degree you agree with the following statement:

I feel competent in managing climate risks on my own farm	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree

9. Please rank the top three items, from the following list of topics, on which you need further support to enable you to take climate friendly actions on your farm [9]

Topic	Rank (identify 1, 2 and 3)
More context information to understand the problem/issue	
Know more about the benefits for me	
Know more about what the implementation of a practice would mean for my farm	
Training on how to implement or use a practice on my farm	
Exchanges with peers and others on how to sustain the adoption of a practice	
Other:....	

Chapter 7

ME&L Outputs

WP3, task 3.3, expects to have the following four outputs based on the CFD ME&L.

Trainings

An inventory of necessary trainings, firstly for CFAs and NCs, will be provided over the course of the CFD project, primarily using the input of the National Annual Meeting group discussions and demonstration Exit Poll.

CSF demonstration improvements

Based on the input from the ME&L, CSF demonstrations will be improved over the course of the project. Therefore, the ME&L strategy will be adapted based on the interim ME&L results.

Leaflets

Using the ME&L we want to learn about 'how to specifically demonstrate CSF practices?'. Leaflets will be made based on the ME&L collection of examples of high quality and impact demonstration possibilities for a specific climate issue. These leaflets can be used as good examples in demonstrating climate action for further use in and beyond the CFD project. The design of the leaflets is done in collaboration with WP1 and distributed via WP8.

Recommendations for Climate Farm Demo activities

At the end of the CFD project, Task 3.3 delivers recommendations for Climate Farm Demo activities (D3.4) in collaboration with Task 3.5.

Reference list

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